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NOTE

Evaluation of the *ex-situ* bioremediation of the petroleum hydrocarbons contaminated soil

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to effectively decontaminate fuel oil-contaminated soil using *ex-situ* bioremediation. Soil samples (contaminated with waste oils) from Serbia were treated. The results showed several significant changes after bioremediation. The pH levels became slightly more alkaline (7.0–7.5). Reduction in organic substance (34%) and carbonate (36%) were observed, respectively. The concentration of n-hexane extractable substances and total petroleum hydrocarbons decreased by around 90%, including a significant reduction in hydrocarbons containing 17C and 18C atoms. Total carbon, organic carbon, and total hydrogen content also decreased notably. The presence of a high number of microorganisms indicated active aerobic and anaerobic processes in the soil. Overall, the results confirmed a high degree of feasibility of the applied conditions for bioremediation of soil contaminated with waste oils.

KEYWORDS

Bioremediation; *ex-situ*; fuel oil; petroleum hydrocarbons; soil contamination; soil remediation

HIGHLIGHTS

After bioremediation:

- the loss of organic substances was about 34%;
- the loss of carbonate was about 36%;
- the value of n-hexane extractable substance decreased by ~90%;
- the total petroleum hydrocarbons content decreased by ~90%;
- the content of hydrocarbons pristane and phytane was drastically reduced;
- the soil contaminated with fuel oil was successfully cleaned.

Introduction

Over the past century, irresponsible waste disposal has caused significant environmental problems. There is now a growing public interest in addressing these issues. The sheer volume of

waste in the environment exceeds the capacity of natural self-purification processes (Miller and Spoolman, 2018). Consequently, it is crucial to remediate polluted areas and restore them to their original state. However, many existing methods

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generate additional waste, highlighting the need for controlled disposal practices (Mirsal 2004).

One of the technologies that are increasingly used in the world for the remediation of polluted environments, primarily soil, is bioremediation (Parus et al. 2023). By applying the process of bioremediation, the degree of purification is up to 98% (Chunyan et al. 2023). Bioremediation is especially effective in the remediation of environments contaminated with oil (petroleum) and oil derivatives (Patowary, Devi, and Mukherjee 2023), but it is also used for the treatment of waste that has not yet reached the environment, and it is increasingly used for environments contaminated with toxic elements (Preetha et al. 2023). It is crucial to recognize that the cumulative impact of petroleum hydrocarbons can have severe health consequences for future generations, including potential risks of cancer, mutations, and developmental abnormalities. (Hossain et al. 2022).

Using nonpathogenic microorganisms for bioremediation is an effective method. These microorganisms naturally present at polluted sites can convert organic pollutants into harmless substances, ensuring safety for humans and the environment. Through this process, organic pollutants are transformed into carbon dioxide and water, while toxic elements are converted into nontoxic forms (Narayanan, Samir Ali, and El-Sheekh 2023).

Using microorganisms from the contamination site is ideal for bioremediation, although microorganisms from other environments can also be used. Collaborative action among multiple strains of microorganisms, forming a consortium, is often necessary to break down pollutants effectively. Microorganisms play a crucial role as "biological agents" in purifying, safeguarding, and preserving the environment (Chunyan et al. 2023).

The aim of this study was to examine the possibility of remediation of soil polluted by oil and its derivatives, using specific strains of microorganisms and bioremediation conditions. The study conducted a six-month *ex-situ* bioremediation experiment on highly polluted soil near Belgrade.

Materials and methods

Characteristics of the study area

The soil sample under examination originated from various locations in Serbia, where it had been contaminated with waste oils from petroleum products. The contaminated soil was transported to Dobanovci, Serbia, and subjected to the *ex-situ* bioremediation process at the plant located in Dobanovci (coordinates: N 44°48'52.42", E 20°13'13.08"). Dobanovci is a suburban neighborhood situated within Belgrade's Surčin municipality. Belgrade, the capital of Serbia, is positioned at the confluence of the Sava and Danube rivers, where the Pannonian Plain meets the Balkan Peninsula (coordinates: N 44°49'4.13", E 20°27'24.83") as depicted in Figure 1.

Preparation of the bio-pile for *ex-situ* bioremediation of fuel oil contaminated soil

Bioremediation bio-pile was prepared according to Beškoski et al. (2011) with some modifications. A bioremediation bio-pile was constructed on a waterproof asphalt surface with dimensions of 1000 m³ and 1250 m², weighing approximately 15,000 tons (as shown in Figure 2(A)). The bio-pile comprised a mixture of soil contaminated with waste oil, including expired oil or oil previously used in engines and subsequently discarded. Consequently, the bio-pile contained oil

Figure 1. Geographical position of Dobanovci.

Figure 2. (A) Preparation of bioremediation bio-pile. (B) Bio-pile inoculation and biostimulation.

hydrocarbons. To enhance porosity, 300 m³ of river sand was incorporated into the bio-pile.

For the sake of uniformity, the bio-pile was thoroughly mixed using a bulldozer and then leveled using a tractor. The final dimensions of the bio-pile measured 75 × 20 × 0.5–0.8 m (length × width × height). Biostimulation was employed to achieve the optimal nutrient ratio of C:N:P:K (100:10:1:0.1). This involved spraying dissolved ammonium nitrate, ammonium phosphate, and potassium chloride evenly throughout the bio-pile (as illustrated in Figure 2(B)). The bio-pile consisted of 1000 m³ of bioremediation substrate.

Throughout the bioremediation process, spanning six months, the bio-pile underwent regular soaking, rotation, and mixing every 15 d to maintain the necessary moisture and aeration levels. Additionally, the bio-pile was inoculated every 30 d with a carefully prepared consortium of microorganisms (*Pseudomonas sp.*, *Bacillus sp.*, *Rhodococcus sp.*, *Brevibacterium sp.*). Detailed information on the isolation, identification, and cultivation processes can be found in our previous works (Gojgic-Cvijovic et al. 2012).

After mixing, the bio-pile was covered with plastic polyethylene foil to avoid the direct influence of weather conditions. BioSolve CLEAR (BioSolve™ Company, USA) was also added to a holder in a volume of 70 mL of the original solution per cubic meter (which has the role of making "non-polar" pollutant molecules available to microorganisms). Chemical and microbiological indicators of bioremediation were monitored immediately after the preparation of the bio-pile and at the end of the bioremediation procedure which lasted for 6 months. At the beginning of

the experiment (before the addition of microorganisms), a control sample of 10 m³ of bio-pile was separated, which was also chemically and microbiologically analyzed.

Soil sampling

Soil samples were sampled with a soil auger (Eijkelkamp, Netherlands) with a depth of 0–70 cm. Sampling was performed from several positions on the bio-piles before/and after the bioremediation/control bio-pile, and then the samples from the same bio-pile were mixed and homogenized (Beškoski et al. 2011). The individual composite samples thus obtained were used for analysis. Microbiological analyzes of all the samples were performed immediately upon delivery to the laboratory, and chemical and physico-chemical ones within 12–24 h (Paetz and Wilke, 2005).

Analytical methods

Determination of the percentage of hygroscopic moisture

The moisture percentage was determined in a hygrometer (model MOC-120H; Shimadzu Co., Japan) with a sample drying program at 105 °C, 1.5 h (ISO 11465 1993).

Potentiometric determination of pH value

The pH of the solid samples was measured in a suspension prepared from a homogenized sample and boiled demineralized water in a ratio of 1:2.5 after 30 min of stirring on a magnetic stirrer according to the standard method (ISO 10390 2005). The measurement was performed on a

digital pH meter (type pH 300; WTW, Weilhem, Germany) with a combined electrode from the same manufacturer.

Determination of ash content

The ash content was determined in porcelain crucibles by burning the organic substance of the sample using a burner until the cessation of white vapor evolution, and then heating in an oven at 550 °C and 800 °C for 2 h. Determination of ash at 550 °C was done in order to determine the loss of organic substance, while, determining the ash at 800 °C showed the loss of carbonate (by subtracting the ash content (%) from 100%).

Determination of inorganic carbon content

The inorganic carbon content of the samples was determined by the standard volumetric method (ISO 10693 1995).

Elemental analysis

The total content of: carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulfur were determined from the dry powdered substance by an automatic analyzer (Vario EL III, CHNS-O, Elemental, Germany). The inorganic carbon content was calculated on the basis of CO₂ content, while the organic carbon content was calculated as the difference between the total and inorganic carbon content (Wilke, Margesin, and Schinner 2005).

Gravimetric determination of total petroleum hydrocarbons

Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) were extracted according to ISO 16703 (ISO EN 16703 2018) and gravimetrically determined according to DIN EN 14354 (DIN EN 14345-12 2004) and Beškoski et al. (Beškoski et al. 2011). Briefly, the hydrocarbons were extracted with a mixture of n-heptane and acetone (2:1) and afterwards washed in a separatory funnel. The aqueous fraction, and with it everything that was dissolved in acetone, was discarded. The n-heptane fraction was further purified by passing through a column with previously inflicted florasil and anhydrous sodium sulfate (which actually acted as a specific filter). Sodium sulfate removed excess water, and florasil retained soil pigments. The heptane layer was collected in a weighing bottle, the substance was

dried in a stream of nitrogen and then the mass was measured.

Gas chromatographic determination (GC) of petroleum hydrocarbons

Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) were determined according to ISO 16703 (ISO EN 16703 2018). This International Standard is applicable to the determination of hydrocarbons from C₁₀-C₄₀ and is not applicable to the quantitative determination of hydrocarbons < C₁₀. The gas chromatographic analyses were conducted on a gas chromatograph – Agilent 7890 A (United States) with a flame ionization detector (FID). A film chromatographic column HP-5 (30 m long, 0.32 mm in diameter, 0.25 μm thickness of stationary phase) was used. The carrier gas was hydrogen at a velocity of 30 cm/s. The chromatographic conditions were as follows: the starting temperature was 60 °C, the injector temperature was 250 °C, and the detector temperature was 300 °C; the temperature was ramped up at 4 °C/min. For data processing ChemStation, Agilent Technologies software was used

Determination of n-hexane extractable substances

n-Hexane extractable substances (HES) were determined by the modified EPA method (US EPA 1998). Briefly, hexane-soluble substances were extracted with n-hexane next, the extract was evaporated on an evaporator and then (with gentle rinsing with n-hexane) passed through a column with previously inflicted florasil and anhydrous sodium sulfate. The mass of the n-hexane fraction was measured.

Biological parameters

In all microbiological procedures, the rules of work in microbiological chemistry were followed, and substances of purity pro analysis were used for the preparation of microbiological media. All microbiological media were prepared by suspending and/or dissolving the components in distilled water and autoclaved to 0.10 MPa for 20 min. In all media, the pH was adjusted by the addition of H₂SO₄ or NaOH (1 M).

Total hemoorganoheterotrophic mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria (TB) were determined on nutrient agar. Nutrient agar

was prepared by dissolving the dry medium according to the manufacturer's instructions. Total anaerobic mesophilic hemoorganoheterotrophic bacteria (AN) were determined on nutrient agar with 0.5% glucose by seeding under anaerobic conditions. The total number of yeasts and spores of molds (YM) was determined on malt agar which was prepared by dissolving the dry medium according to the manufacturer's instructions. Hydrocarbon-degrading microorganisms (HD) were determined on a mineral hydrocarbon medium with diesel D2 (UG) as the sole carbon source (Milcic-Terzic et al. 2000).

The number of microorganisms was determined by the method of serial dilution (Qayyum et al. 2020). Total grown colonies of hemoorganoheterotrophic mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria (TB), as well as total anaerobic mesophilic hemoorganoheterotrophic bacteria (AN) were counted after 48 h. Yeasts and spores of molds (YM) were counted after 72 h, while colonies of microorganisms that decompose hydrocarbons (HD) were counted after 7–8 days. The seeded agar plates were incubated at 28 °C.

Statistical analysis

Data are expressed as the mean and standard deviation of two replicates. Pearson's correlation coefficients ($p < .05$) among different parameters were computed to assess the relationships among these parameters. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $p < .05$, followed by Tukey's test, was applied to assess the effectivity of the bioremediation. Statistica software version 8.0 (StatSoft Co., Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA) was applied for statistical analysis.

Results and discussion

Chemical analyzes of soil before and after the bioremediation process

The tested samples were found to contain 28.8–30.3% moisture (Table 1). Literature data indicate that moisture has a strong effect on biochemical processes in contaminated soils (Myazin et al. 2021). The moisture content of the bio-pile during bioremediation was within the limits that are optimal for this technique (Gupta et al. 2021).

Table 1. Moisture and ash content (%) and pH value of the examined soil.

Tested parameter	Initial state	After bioremediation	Control sample
Moisture	30.32 ± 0.68 ^a	29.58 ± 0.81 ^{a,b}	28.76 ± 0.25 ^b
Ash (550 °C)	65.64 ± 1.10 ^a	96.34 ± 0.64 ^b	65.18 ± 1.68 ^a
Ash (800 °C)	63.46 ± 0.53 ^a	95.79 ± 0.53 ^b	63.91 ± 0.01 ^a
pH	7.0 ± 0.06 ^a	7.9 ± 0.06 ^b	7.3 ± 0.06 ^a

Ash is expressed on dry matter.

Means in the same row with different roman letters in superscript are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The ash content of the samples after incineration at 550 °C ranged from 65.2% to 96.3%, while at 800 °C it ranged from 63.5% to 95.8% (Table 1). The loss of organic substance and carbonate after incineration was observed. The sample before bioremediation and the control sample had a loss of approximately 34% and 36% of organic substance and carbonate, respectively, after incineration at 550 °C and 800 °C (Table 2). In contrast, the soil sample after bioremediation showed a much lower loss of 3.66% of organic substance and 4.21% of carbonate after incineration at the respective temperatures (Table 2).

The ash content did not differ significantly between the samples before bioremediation and the control sample at both incineration temperatures (Table 1). The increase in ash content by around 30% in the samples was associated with a significant reduction in organic matter and carbonate in the bioremediated soil after incineration at 550 °C and 800 °C, respectively.

The significant loss of organic substance (~30%) and carbonate (~30%) after incineration at the respective temperatures indicates the high success rate of the bioremediation process, highlighting efficient microbial activity in removing organic pollutants. The organic matter content in the bioremediated soil was approximately 30% lower than that of the control sample. However, the ash content in the samples before bioremediation was similar to the control sample and showed no statistical differences.

Statistical differences were observed in the ash content between the soil samples without bioremediation and the control sample, depending on the incineration temperature. The ash content reflects the burning of organic and inorganic carbon, which are important parameters for assessing bioremediation success alongside other content measurements. Correlation analysis

Table 2. Content of organic substances, carbonate, n-hexane extractable substance and total petroleum hydrocarbons of the examined soil.

Tested parameter	Initial state	After bioremediation	Control sample
%			
Organic substances (Loss of ignition at 550 °C)	34.36 ± 1.10 ^a	3.66 ± 0.64 ^b	34.82 ± 1.68 ^a
Carbonate (Loss of ignition at 800 °C)	36.54 ± 0.68 ^a	4.21 ± 0.53 ^b	36.09 ± 0.25 ^a
g/kg			
HES ¹	24.02 ± 0.79 ^a	2.34 ± 0.17 ^b	23.45 ± 0.88 ^a
TPH ²	22.82 ± 0.66 ^a	1.62 ± 0.14 ^b	22.13 ± 0.83 ^a

The results are given on dry matter.

¹HES – n-Hexane Extractable Substances.

²TPH – Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons.

Means in the same row with different roman letters in superscript are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

indicated a strong relationship between the ash content at both incineration temperatures, suggesting a consistent trend in the loss of organic and inorganic carbon. The ash content also showed a strong inverse correlation with moisture content in the samples, indicating that higher moisture content corresponded to lower ash content.

The pH values of the samples ranged from 7.0 to 7.5 (Table 1). Soil pH plays a crucial role in biodegradation by influencing microbial activity, enzyme function, and microbial community diversity (Myazin et al. 2021). The pH values of the soil samples before bioremediation and the control sample were similar and did not show significant differences. After bioremediation, the soil exhibited a slight increase in alkalinity, which could be attributed to microbial activity and the buffering effect of certain cationic substances (such as potassium, calcium, magnesium, etc.) (Myazin et al. 2021). However, all samples maintained a pH range optimal for microbial growth (pH = 6–8) and oil degradation (pH = 6.5–8) (Myazin et al. 2021).

Statistical analysis revealed a strong correlation between soil pH values and ash content ($r = 0.87$), as well as moisture content ($r = -0.87$), although these relationships did not reach statistical significance at a p -value of .05 (Table 3).

The n-hexane extractable substances (HES) content in the sample before bioremediation and the control sample was approximately 23–24% (Table 2). After bioremediation, the HES content in the soil sample decreased to around 2%. The HES fraction represents alkanes eluted with n-hexane solvent. Comparing the initial HES content in the soil before bioremediation (24.0 g/kg), which was considered 100%, the HES content in

Table 3. Correlation coefficients between some properties^a.

Relationship	r
Ash (550 °C) – ash (800 °C)	1.00
Ash (550 °C) – moisture	-1.00
Ash (800 °C) – moisture	-1.00
Ash (550 °C) – pH value	0.87 ^b
Ash (800 °C) – pH value	0.87 ^b
Moisture – pH value	-0.87 ^b
TPH ¹ – HES ²	1.00
$C_{total} - C_{organic}$	1.00
$C_{total} - C_{inorganic}$	1.00
$N_{total} - C_{total}$	1.00
$N_{total} - C_{organic}$	1.00
$N_{total} - C_{inorganic}$	1.00
$N_{total} - H_{total}$	-1.00
$S_{total} - C_{total}$	-1.00
$S_{total} - C_{organic}$	-1.00
$S_{total} - C_{inorganic}$	-1.00
$S_{total} - N_{total}$	-1.00

^aSignificant et $p < .05$. ^bNot significant et $p < .05$.

¹HES – n-hexane extractable substance.

²TPH – Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons.

the soil after bioremediation decreased by 90.3%. In contrast, the HES content in the control sample only decreased by 2.4% compared to the soil sample before bioremediation. These findings are consistent with the results reported by Li et al. (Li et al. 2023) it can be assumed that the presence of yeast in the inoculation medium contributed to such a successful removal of HES. Namely, these authors, after biostimulation–bioaugmentation with yeast, achieved an n-alkane removal effect of 71.5–100% in petroleum-contaminated soils. The content of HES and TPH were very strongly correlated ($r = 1.00$; Table 3).

The initial TPH content in the soil sample before bioremediation and the control sample was approximately 22% (Table 2). After bioremediation, the TPH content decreased to 1.62%. The bioremediation process achieved a remarkable 92.9% reduction in TPH content, whereas the control sample only showed a 3.02% decrease. These results demonstrate the effective performance of the applied microorganisms in

Figure 3. GC spectrum of extracted petroleum hydrocarbons before bioremediation.

Figure 4. GC spectrum of extracted petroleum hydrocarbons before bioremediation.

bioremediation. The substantial decrease in TPH content in the soil after bioremediation is consistent with findings reported in the literature. (Rondon-Afanador et al. 2023).

GC-analysis detected petroleum hydrocarbons in the soil using Figures 3 and 4. The gas chromatograms displayed peaks representing TPH with carbon atom ranges of 14–40, both before and after bioremediation. Peaks in the C14–C28 range indicated low-molecular-weight hydrocarbons, while peaks in the C28–C40 range indicated high-molecular-weight hydrocarbons. After bioremediation, there was a significant decrease in the size of both light and heavy TPH peaks on the GC chromatograms (Figure 5). Initially, the soil sample contained notable amounts of hydrocarbons with 17 and 18 carbon atoms, specifically pristane (C17) and phytane (C18; Figure 3).

However, after bioremediation, there was a substantial reduction in the levels of these petroleum hydrocarbons (Figure 4). These results demonstrate a highly successful bioremediation process with a favorable potential, characterized by a significant number of bacteria capable of efficiently degrading hydrocarbons compared to the overall bacterial population. These microorganisms utilize hydrocarbons as an energy source for their growth. (Adetunji et al. 2021).

The initial total carbon content in the samples and the control was around 17% (Table 4). However, after bioremediation, it significantly decreased to 3.66% (Table 4). Inorganic carbon content remained consistently below 1% for all samples (Table 4), while organic carbon content was determined by the difference between total carbon and inorganic carbon. The soil sample

Figure 5. Comparative view of GC chromatograms before (A) and after bioremediation.

Table 4. Results of elemental organic analysis (%).

Test parameter	Initial state	After bioremediation	Control sample
C _{total}	17.27 ± 0.29 ^a	1.29 ± 0.28 ^b	17.51 ± 0.27 ^a
C _{organic}	17.00 ± 0.28 ^a	0.53 ± 0.26 ^b	16.80 ± 0.26 ^a
C _{inorganic}	0.27 ± 0.01 ^a	0.76 ± 0.02 ^a	0.71 ± 0.02 ^a
N _{total}	1.05 ± 0.07 ^a	1.15 ± 0.11 ^a	1.11 ± 0.04 ^a
H _{total}	3.45 ± 0.15 ^a	0.13 ± 0.02 ^b	3.65 ± 0.05 ^a
S _{total}	0.07 ± 0.01 ^a	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a	0.07 ± 0.01 ^a

The results are on dry matter.

Means in the same row with different roman letters in superscript are significantly different ($p < .05$).

after bioremediation also had organic carbon content below 1% (Table 4). Before bioremediation, the samples and control had an organic carbon content of approximately 17% (Table 4). Statistical and elemental analysis found no significant differences in total carbon content between the soil before bioremediation and the control. However, after bioremediation, there was a 92.5% decrease in total carbon content compared to the initial condition and a 92.6% decrease compared to the control (Table 4). Similar trends were observed for organic carbon content, with a decrease of 96.88% in the soil after bioremediation compared to the initial state and 96.85% compared to the control (Table 4). There were no significant differences in inorganic carbon content before and after bioremediation, as well as compared to the control (Table 4). Correlation analysis indicated a strong relationship ($r=1.00$) between total carbon content, organic carbon content, and inorganic carbon content (Table 3).

The total nitrogen and sulfur content did not change significantly during bioremediation. Initial soil contamination was evident from the high total nitrogen content, exceeding the average content in the soil. The ratio of total carbon to

nitrogen differed significantly among the samples. The soil before bioremediation and the control sample had a high ratio, while the soil after bioremediation showed a low ratio (Table 4). Soil contaminated with organic pollutants typically exhibits a high carbon-to-nitrogen ratio. Bioremediation did not significantly affect the total nitrogen content. A strong correlation was observed between total nitrogen and total/organic/inorganic carbon content, as well as total hydrogen (Table 3). The total sulfur content remained practically unchanged before and after bioremediation, suggesting the absence of sulfate-reducing microorganisms in the applied consortium. Such microorganisms are commonly used to mitigate acid waste in mining tailings (Ayangbenro, Olanrewaju, and Babalola 2018).

The hydrogen content in the samples before bioremediation and the control sample was approximately 3% (Table 4). However, after bioremediation, the hydrogen content decreased to less than 1% (Table 4). There was a significant difference in hydrogen content between the soil samples before bioremediation and the control sample compared to the sample after bioremediation. No statistical difference was observed in sulfur content between these samples (Table 4). Correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship ($r=1.00$) between hydrogen content and all examined parameters in the elemental organic analysis, except for sulfur content. A strong negative correlation was found between sulfur content and all parameters examined in the elemental organic analysis of the soil ($r=-1.00$; Table 3). These correlations are expected as hydrogen plays a crucial role in microbial activities and global element cycles.

Table 5. Results of microbiological analysis.

Test parameter	Initial state	After bioremediation	Control sample
cfu ³ /g			
TB ^b	2×10^9	4×10^8	7×10^7
YM ^c	2×10^6	3×10^4	9×10^5
HD ^d	7×10^7	2×10^6	2×10^5
AN ^e	4×10^3	9×10^3	1×10^4
%			
Bioremediation potential (HD/TB 100)	3.5	0.5	0.3

The results are on dry matter.

^acfu/g – colony forming unit

^bTB – total hemoorganoheterotrophic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria.

^cYM – yeasts, spores and molds.

^dHD – bacteria that degrade (decompose) hydrocarbons.

^eAN – anaerobic bacteria.

Hydrogen serves as an electron donor for the reduction of pollutants, impacting the structure and function of microbial communities (Teng et al. 2019). Probably for this reason, there was a very significant decrease (96.2%) in the total hydrogen content in the tested sample after bioremediation.

Analysis of bacterial count of the examined soil

The presence of total hemoorganoheterotrophic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria in the soil before bioremediation was 2×10^9 cfu/g, and after bioremediation, it was 4×10^8 cfu/g. In the control sample, the presence of these microorganisms was 7×10^7 cfu/g (Table 5). The presence of yeasts, spores, and molds in the soil before bioremediation was 2×10^6 cfu/g, and after bioremediation, it was 3×10^4 cfu/g. In the control sample, the presence of these microorganisms was 9×10^5 cfu/g (Table 5). The presence of bacteria that degrade hydrocarbons in the soil before bioremediation was 7×10^7 cfu/g, and after bioremediation, it was 2×10^6 cfu/g. In the control sample, the presence of these microorganisms was 2×10^5 cfu/g (Table 5). The presence of anaerobic bacteria in the soil before bioremediation was 4×10^3 cfu/g, and after bioremediation, it was 9×10^3 cfu/g. In the control sample, the presence of these microorganisms was 1×10^5 cfu/g (Table 5).

The high number of microorganisms in the soil samples indicated active aerobic and anaerobic processes. The total hemoorganoheterotrophic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria remained consistently high before and after bioremediation (Table 5). Similarly, a significant

number of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria were present in the soil samples before and after bioremediation, with a slightly lower count in the control sample.

The number of microorganisms can vary depending on the bioremediation conditions and duration. The use of additives and biostimulation procedures can also impact the microbial population. (Kahraman et al. 2017). The addition of nutrients has been found to increase microorganism numbers. Additionally, maintaining a high density of bacteria is crucial for efficient bioremediation (Balseiro-Romero et al. 2019).

The HD/TB ratio is crucial for assessing the bioremediation potential, indicating the capacity for contaminant decomposition (Gojgić-Cvijović et al. 2006). The soil prepared for bioremediation showed a high bioremediation potential in its initial state, leading to significant hydrocarbon decomposition during the process. In contrast, the control sample without added microorganisms exhibited the lowest bioremediation potential (Table 5).

Conclusion

Bioremediation effectively reduced organic matter, total and organic carbon content in the soil, as confirmed by analytical methods. The presence of n-hexane extractable substances and total petroleum hydrocarbons decreased by approximately 90%, indicating the efficiency of the applied microorganisms. The initial soil sample had significant hydrocarbon presence, which decreased after bioremediation. The abundance of microorganisms indicated active aerobic and anaerobic processes in the soil. These results demonstrate

the successful application of bioremediation in cleaning petroleum-contaminated soil. Soil protection is crucial for future generations, considering the challenge of preserving soil quality and the significant amount of environmental waste that cannot be naturally removed.

All authors contributed to the study conception and design, all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript and all authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Authors' contributions

Andjela B. Stanojevic – material preparation, bioremediation, data collection and analysis, and writing-original draft. **Miroslav Vrvic** – suggested the theme of the work. **Jirina Szakova** – supervision, resources (supporting). **Srdan Miletic** – material preparation, bioremediation, data collection and analysis and resources (supporting).

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References

- Adetunji, C., Oluwaseun, O. Anthony Anani, and D. Panpatte. 2021. Mechanism of actions involved in sustainable ecorestoration of petroleum hydrocarbons polluted soil by the beneficial microorganism. In *Microbial rejuvenation of polluted environment microorganisms for sustainability*, ed. D. G. Panpatte and Y. K. Jhala, 189–206. Singapore: Springer. doi: [10.1007/978-981-15-7455-9_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7455-9_8).
- Ayangbenro, A. S., O. S. Olanrewaju, and O. O. Babalola. 2018. Sulfate-reducing bacteria as an effective tool for sustainable acid mine bioremediation. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 9:1986. doi: [10.3389/fmicb.2018.01986](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.01986).
- Balseiro-Romero, M., C. Monterroso, P. S. Kidd, T. A. Lu-Chau, P. Gkorezis, J. Vangronsveld, and J. J. Casares. 2019. Modelling the ex situ bioremediation of diesel-contaminated soil in a slurry bioreactor using a hydrocarbon-degrading inoculant. *Journal of Environmental Management* 246:840–8. doi: [10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.06.034](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.06.034).
- Beškoski, V. P., G. Gojgić-Cvijović, J. Milić, M. Ilić, S. Miletić, T. Šolević, M. M. Vrvic, T. Solević, M. M. Vrvic, Š. Tatjana, et al. 2011. Ex situ bioremediation of a soil contaminated by mazut (heavy residual fuel oil) – A field experiment. *Chemosphere* 83 (1):34–40. doi: [10.1016/j.chemosphere.2011.01.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2011.01.020).
- Chunyan, X., M. A. Qaria, X. Qi, and Z. Daochen. 2023. the role of microorganisms in petroleum degradation: Current development and prospects. *The Science of the Total Environment* 865:161112. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.161112](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.161112).
- DIN EN 14345-12. 2004. DIN EN 14345:2004-12 Characterization of waste - Determination of hydrocarbon content by gravimetry.
- Gojgić-Cvijović, G. D., J. S. Milic, T. M. Solevic, V. P. Beskoski, M. V. Ilic, L. S. Djokic, T. M. Narancic, and M. M. Vrvic. 2012. Biodegradation of petroleum sludge and petroleum polluted soil by a bacterial consortium: A laboratory study. *Biodegradation* 23 (1):1–14. doi: [10.1007/s10532-011-9481-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10532-011-9481-1).
- Gojgić-Cvijović, G., V. Beškoski, J. Milić, M. Ilić, T. Šolević, S. Miletić, I. Vučković, B. Potkonjak, B. Jovančičević, M. Radulović, et al. 2006. Isolation, selection and adaptation of zymogenous microorganisms: A basis of successful bioremediation. In *Scientific gathering: Implementation of remediation in environmental quality improvement*, ed. L. Tanasijević, 125–32. Belgrade, Serbia: Chamber of Commerce, Board of Environmental Protection and Sustainable Development. <https://cer.ihtm.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/4991>.
- Gupta, P. K., B. Yadav, B. K. Yadav, S. Sushkova, and S. Basu. 2021. Engineered bioremediation of napl polluted sites: experimental and simulation-optimization approach under heterogeneous moisture and temperature conditions. *Journal of Environmental Engineering* 147 (8): 04021023. doi: [10.1061/\(ASCE\)EE.1943-7870.0001891](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0001891).
- Hossain, M. F., M. A. Akter, M. S. R. Sohan, D. N. Sultana, M. A. Reza, and K. M. F. Hoque. 2022. Bioremediation potential of hydrocarbon degrading bacteria: isolation, characterization, and assessment. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 29 (1):211–6. doi: [10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.08.069](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.08.069).
- ISO 10390. 2005. Soil quality—Determination of pH.
- ISO 10693. 1995. Soil quality—Determination of carbonate content—Volumetric method.
- ISO 11465. 1993. Soil quality—Determination of dry matter and water content on a mass basis—Gravimetric method.
- ISO EN 16703. 2018. Kvalitet Zemljišta - Određivanje Sadržaja Ugljovodonika u Opsegu Od C10 Do C40 Gasnom Hromatografijom.

- Kahraman, B. F., A. Altin, S. Altin, and G. Demirel Bayik. 2017. Biostimulation of n -alkane degradation in diesel fuel-spiked soils. *Soil and Sediment Contamination* 26 (5): 486–500. doi: [10.1080/15320383.2017.1355351](https://doi.org/10.1080/15320383.2017.1355351).
- Li, C., C. Cui, J. Zhang, J. Shen, B. He, Y. Long, and J. Ye. 2023. Biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons based pollutants in contaminated soil by exogenous effective microorganisms and indigenous microbiome. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 253:114673. doi: [10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.114673](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.114673).
- Milcic-Terzic, J., Y. Lopez-Vidal, M. M. Vrvic, and S. Saval. 2000. Biodegradation potential assessment of microbial consortia isolated from a diesel-contaminated soil. *Water Science and Technology* 42 (5–6):403–6. doi: [10.2166/wst.2000.0541](https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2000.0541).
- Miller, T. G., and S. E. Spoolman. 2018. Solid and hazardous waste. In *Living i the environment*, ed. D. M. Giovanniello, 19th ed., 572–601. Boston, USA: Cengage Learning.
- Mirsal, I. A. 2004. Soil remediation. In *Soil pollution, origin, monitoring and remediation*, ed. A. Oelschläger, 263–81. Springer.
- Myazin, V. A., M. V. Korneykova, A. A. Chaporgina, N. V. Fokina, and G. K. Vasilyeva. 2021. The Effectiveness of biostimulation, bioaugmentation and sorption-biological treatment of soil contaminated with petroleum products in the Russian subarctic. *Microorganisms* 9 (8):1722. doi: [10.3390/microorganisms9081722](https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081722).
- Narayanan, M., S. Samir Ali, and M. El-Sheekh. 2023. A comprehensive review on the potential of microbial enzymes in multipollutant bioremediation: mechanisms, challenges, and future prospects. *Journal of Environmental Management* 334:117532. doi: [10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117532](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117532).
- Parus, A., T. Ciesielski, M. Woźniak-Karczewska, M. Ślachciński, M. Owsianiak, Ł. Ławniczak, A. P. Loibner, H. J. Heipieper, and Ł. Chrzanowski. 2023. Basic principles for biosurfactant-assisted (bio)remediation of soils contaminated by heavy metals and petroleum hydrocarbons – A critical evaluation of the performance of rhamnolipids. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 443 (pt A): 130171. doi: [10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.130171](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.130171).
- Paetz, A., and B. Wilke. 2005. Soil sampling and storage. In *Manual for soil analysis-monitoring and assessing soil bioremediation*, eds. R. Margesin and F. Schinner, 1–45. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag.
- Patowary, R., A. Devi, and A. K. Mukherjee. 2023. Advanced bioremediation by an amalgamation of nanotechnology and modern artificial intelligence for efficient restoration of crude petroleum oil-contaminated sites: A prospective study. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 30 (30):74459–84. doi: [10.1007/s11356-023-27698-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-27698-4).
- Preetha, J. S. Y., M. Arun, N. Vidya, K. Kowsalya, J. Halka, and G. Ondrasek. 2023. Biotechnology advances in bioremediation of arsenic: A review. *Molecules* 28 (3):1474. doi: [10.3390/molecules28031474](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28031474).
- Qayyum, S., S. Basharat, A. Hussain Mian, S. Qayum, M. Ali, P. Changsheng, M. Shahzad, and F. Sultan. 2020. Isolation, identification and antibacterial study of pigmented bacteria. *Applied Nanoscience* 10 (12):4495–503. doi: [10.1007/s13204-020-01363-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13204-020-01363-5).
- Rondon-Afanador, C., G. Pinilla-Meza, F. C. Casallas-Cuervo, C. Diaz-Vanegas, D. Barreto-Gomez, C. Benavides, N. Buitrago, M. Calvo, C. Forero-Forero, V. Galvis-Ibarra, et al. 2023. Bioremediation of heavy oily sludge: A microcosms study. *Biodegradation* 34 (1):1–20. doi: [10.1007/s10532-022-10006-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10532-022-10006-1).
- Teng, Y., Y. Xu, X. Wang, and P. Christie. 2019. Function of biohydrogen metabolism and related microbial communities in environmental bioremediation. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10:106. doi: [10.3389/fmicb.2019.00106](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00106).
- Us Epa, O. L. E. M. 1998. SW-846 Test Method 9071B: N -Hexane Extractable Material (HEM) for Sludge, Sediment, and Solid Samples.
- Wilke, B.-M., R. Margesin, and F. Schinner. 2005. Determination of chemical and physical soil properties. In *Monitoring and assessing soil bioremediation: soil biology* Vol. 5, 47–95. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer. doi: [10.1007/3-540-28904-6_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-28904-6_2).